

Uncertainty analysis of wave energy farms financial indicators

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Abstract

In this work, an analysis of the uncertainty that influences wave energy farm financial returns is carried out. Firstly, a methodology to analyze the financial uncertainty through cash flow analysis is developed. A reconstruction of a set of power production life-cycles is made based on the methodology proposed in [1] using a selection and an interpolation technique. This set of life cycles allowed to obtain the statistical distributions of the main financial indicators (IRR, NPV and PBP). The high variability of these parameters is explained by the climate variability. Therefore, for the economic study of a wave energy project the influence of the climate conditions is demonstrated and for this purpose a long climate data series is needed. Finally, a second uncertainty source related with the political and legislation environment is studied, focusing on the effect of feed in tariff. This sensitivity analysis of the feed in tariffs is made based on cash-flow algorithm. Current feed in tariffs seemed insufficient in order to get profitable wave energy projects and also an increase in feed in tariff resulted in an increase of variability of financial indicators. Therefore an increase in feed in tariff is not recommended for early stage technologies. Finally, learning curve was also included in this investigation and it appeared as a key parameter in order to get cost effective financial returns.

Keywords:

Wave interaction, Wave Energy converter, Internal rate of return, Net

1. Introduction

Nowadays wave energy is still in the prototype testing stage. However, the ocean wave energy sector has significant potential to contribute substantially to the global electricity generation if sufficient investment is provided. Furthermore, wave energy represents a good alternative as a renewable source due to the low environmental impacts and the extensive sites available for the placement of wave farms. Current wave energy targets for 2020 are quite ambitious (f.i. 1000 MW for 2020 in the UK or 500 MW for Ireland) making economic assessment of wave energy farms a key issue in the search of financial resources.

A methodology for economic analysis of wave energy projects is therefore required and it is an essential tool for assessing the potential profitability of wave energy projects from the perspective of developers, local administration and investors. Beside costs, developers, investors and public administration's major concern is the assessment of project uncertainties. According to [2] there are three major sources of uncertainty that can affect the profitability of an investment projects.

The first one is related to the high internal variability of the data: met-ocean historical records show a highly variable behavior which origins uncertainty about how seasonal, interannual and long term variability of wave energy flux may affect production over the farm's expected life.

The second source of uncertainty has to do with the fact that most technologies have rarely been tested under real conditions; consequently only simulations of future response and efficiency are possible. Future estimates should consider the reduction in uncertainties thanks to the experience acquired through the learning processes associated with the deployment of WECs.

The last source of uncertainty considered is linked to socioeconomic issues including, among others: institutional support, availability of subsidies for emerging green technologies, future social acceptance or commercial conditions under which energy will be supplied to users. Therefore, a study of

the uncertainties that affect wave energy development is required in order to provide investors a guide to the potential risks assumed on wave energy development.

Several authors have carried out economical studies of wave energy projects ([3],[4],[6]). Almost all of them concerning a specific type of technology.[3] was one of the first to study several arrangements for the Wave Dragon device taking into account the operational and maintenance costs as a function of the marine climate.

[3], studied the economical performance of a generic wave energy device through operational simulations. However, in general all the studies published to date base their cash flow analysis on the power matrix. However, [1] showed that the power matrix is not accurate enough to study the long term behavior of a WEC and neither its economic performance.

Several authors ([4]) have studied the economic feasibility of wave energy projects reaching the same conclusion, namely that current feed in tariffs are not sufficient to make the development of wave energy farms cost-effective. A sensitivity analysis of the inputs of the economic analysis was performed and optimal locations for specific technologies are suggested as a function of these parameters ([5]).

[6] also studied the implications of operational costs on the economic analysis taking into account the concepts of accessibility and availability of a specific location. Finally [4] performed a case study sensitivity analysis taking into account the impact of the learning curve, supply and demand curves and future cost of cash. The conclusion of this study was that the current feed in tariff for wave energy in countries such as Ireland is insufficient to develop cost-effective projects. Ireland feed in tariff, available until 2015, has been set to 0.22 Euros/kWh and spans a 15 year project. However this tariff has been proven to be insufficient for currently available devices, specifically for the Pelamis Device studied by [4]. A feed in tariff of 0.45 Euros/kWh was found to be more realistic in order to reach an attractive internal rate of return.

The goal of this paper is to carry out an uncertainty analysis of the most relevant financial indicators to be considered in wave energy farm develop-

ments. The three sources of uncertainty considered are treated differently. Introducing parametric scenarios for prices and feed in tariffs a sensitivity analysis to different socioeconomic scenarios is carried out. Uncertainties in technological evolution are addressed considering a learning coefficient as is usually done in other energy economic analysis. Much emphasis is put in this work in assessing uncertainties stemming from inter-annual variability of wave climate, one of the most unpredictable sources of uncertainty to date.

Without loss of generality and for the sake of concreteness, the uncertainty analysis is carried out for a specific wave energy converter technology based on a two body heave converter as described in [1].

2. Methodology

2.1. Technology selection

The first step consists of the selection of the technology. The WEC selected is a two body heave converter which extracts energy from the relative motion of both bodies in the heave mode (see Figure 1). This WEC extracts energy with a linear generator with 1 MW of nominal power. The device is based on [7]. This type of technology is currently under development by two different companies. It should be highlighted that although the methodology is applied to this converter, this methodology can be generalized to any WEC technology.

2.2. Wave farm location

The second step in the methodology is the design of a wave energy farm consisting of a number of these devices. Wave energy is an expensive option when compared with other renewable sources. However, under some specific conditions this cost could be admissible. For instance, isolated electrical systems are highly dependent on fossil fuel resulting in high energy costs due to long distances from mainland or developed areas.

In this context, renewable energy sources are very useful in order to achieve self-sufficiency and overexpenses can be assumed. A wave energy resource assessment around the island has been carried out in [8], reaching the conclusion that the northwest coast is the most suitable place for the farm [9] (see figure 2). The selected area is located at a point in La Palma Island with coordinates $28.81N$ and $18.01W$ for its accessibility and clean

Figure 1: Two body heave converter analyzed

exposure to wave energy flux (due to the incidence of the Atlantic swell). This site is 1500 m from the shoreline, at a 150 m depth and has a yearly mean resource of 22 kW/m. The wave climate data of this point has been provided by [10], including the wave height, peak period and wave direction from 1948 to 2008. In figure 3 the occurrence matrix of this location is shown.

2.3. Wave farm production

The methodology to obtain the long-term power production is explained on figure 4, based on [1]. This method provides a way to obtain the life cycle power production of a device with the same computational effort than the classical method based on the multiplication of the power matrix and the occurrence matrix, being able to estimate long-term power production time series. Firstly, the climate data is taken from a global reanalysis database, GOW, with 60 year climate data. A sea state selection technique is applied to this set of data. The MaxDiss selection technique is used from [11] in order to select the power of the most representative sea states only (figure 5). These selected sea states are the input for the time domain model.

Numerically, in order to compute the power production two steps are

Figure 2: Location of the wave farm and yearly mean wave energy resources around La Palma Island extracted from [8]

needed, firstly, the floating converter is analyzed with [12], a Boundary Element Model (BEM), that obtains the added mass, damping and excitation force coefficients. These coefficients are the input for the time domain model described in [1]. With this time domain model, the power production is obtained for the selected sea states. Finally, in order to reconstruct the long-term power production series, an interpolation technique is applied. The Radial Basis Function interpolation technique (RBF) has been used to obtain the complete power series.

This method is validated by comparing one full year of computed sea states using the numerical model with the new methodology applied to 196 selected sea states. This comparison gave a correlation coefficient of 0.96 in [1].

In order to obtain the farm layout for this analysis, a previous study investigated the most important factors that influence array performance ([13]). Optimal configurations for wave energy farms were proposed as a function

Figure 3: Occurrence matrix and selected sea states for the selected site

of the wave climate. In this case, a wave energy farm composed of 4 WECs is analyzed. Following [13], a rhombus configuration is selected for this location. For a multidirectional climate a rhombus configuration is optimal because wakes are less probable with this configuration and constructive interaction is therefore achieved.

Based on the methodology described, the production of the wave farm is computed. The time domain model is run for these sea states resulting in hourly time series of the wave farm production for the last 60 years. This is the input to carry out the life-cycle analysis.

2.4. Life cycle analysis

In order to perform the analysis of the uncertainty of financial indicators on wave energy farms a database of a great number of life-cycle power productions is required. This is necessary because the interannual variability of power production is important and therefore the project profitability is significantly variable. Based on [14], for a given lifetime of n_y years (25 years), n_y years bootstrap sub-samples from the original t_s years (60 years) are selected. The selection is based on Monte Carlo random sampling with replacement.

Figure 4: Diagram of the power production model

The methodology is based on the following Figure 6:

1. From the long term power production module, explained in Figure 4, a 60 year power production series is obtained
2. Random selection is performed based on the previous assumptions (random bootstrapping, Montecarlo technique)
3. 10.000 lifecycles of 25 year duration are generated

A 25 year time is set, as this is the period that this kind of infrastructure is assumed to last in the sea (with an estimated replacement of the devices at the middle of the service life). In this work it is assumed that no replacement of the mooring system is needed based on the experience presented in [15].

Figure 5: Yearly production of the wave farm 1948 to 2008

Figure 6: Process of generation of the life-cycles for the statistic analysis (Monte Carlo)

2.5. Project Budget

In this subsection, a brief description of the theoretical assumptions and the estimates the parameters needed for the economic analysis is given. First, the Engineering, Procurement, Construction and Installation (EPCI) budget

of the wave farm is presented in Table 1. The WEC is assumed to be built of steel and a concrete ballast. Steel price is fixed at 5 Euros/Kg. For concrete a cost of $98.35\text{Euro}/m^3$ is assumed. The cost of the linear generator is set to 600.000 Euros/MW. This last assumption is an important source of uncertainty due to the lack of experience in this field and the limited availability of commercial PTOs for this type of devices in the market. This cost is selected based on the state of the art of the generators in existing WEC prototypes or demonstration projects.

As shown in table 1 and Figure 7 the budget of the project is quite high. The percentage of steel is nearly 37%, representing an important stake of the cost. It would be possible to assume that for WECs that have been through several optimization phases this percentage could be reduced.

Figure 7: Distribution of cost items for the EPCI budget for the selected wave energy farm

In order to complete the economic analysis, operating expenses (OPEX) have to be added. OPEX refers to the operation and maintenance costs also

Concept	Subconcept	Amount (Euro)
Power Take-Off	Procurement	2.400.000
	Onshore installation	0
Platform	Manufacturing	6.671.880
	Equipment and Systems on board	498.953
Station-keeping System	Mooring procurement	851.273
	Anchoring	154.723
	Vessel Mobilization Cost	200.000
	Mooring procurement	765.000
Electrical infrastructure	Offshore Substation	288.666
	Onshore Substation	218.666
	Array cable procurement	168.000
	Array cable installation	765.000
	Export cable procurement	525.000
	Export cable installation	765.000
	Onshore cable procurement	630.000
	Onshore cable installation	490.000
Logistics and Installation	Tug Vessel	270.000
	Supply Vessel	360.000
	Mobilization cost	300.000
	Other	93.000
Engineering		191.494
Contingencies		1.321.494
TOTAL		17.840.000

Table 1: EPCI Budget for the considered wave energy farm

taking into account the insurance cost. OPEX assessment is a difficult task due to the absence of experience in the operation and maintenance of these devices. In order to provide a value a review of the existing percentages with respect to the initial cost of the project is carried out. [6] presented a table compiling OPEX costs in available projects suggesting values ranging between 1.4 % and 7 % of the total project initial cost. In this study an average value of 5 % is taken based on a conservative approach. A total replacement of the devices is proposed at the middle of the life-cycle. A conservative value has been assumed due to the lack of experience regarding the durability of these types of structures at sea.

No project financing is considered and payment of the initial cost of the project is set at year 0 in the cash-flow analysis as it is conventionally assumed in project financing studies(f.i [16]).

2.6. Discounted cash-flow algorithm

The discounted cash flow technique is a method assessing the value of a project, company or asset by measuring the expected future cash flows derived from its operation, introducing the time value of money to capture the opportunity cost of the money tied up in the project. All future cash flows are estimated and discounted to give their present values (*PVs*). The sum of all future cash flows, both incoming and outgoing, is the present value of the project (*PV*), which summarizes in a single value the overall distribution of cash flows derived from the project. The future value, *FV*, of a series of cash flows refers to the future value, at future time *n* (total periods in the future), of the sum of the future values of all cash flows, *CF*.

The cash flow analysis is based on the following formula:

$$PV = \frac{FV}{(1 + r)^t} \quad (1)$$

where *PV* is the present value, *FV* refers to the future value, *r* represents the discount rate and *t* means the number of time periods.

For the uncertainty analysis of the financial performance that will be presented in the next section a set of 3 financial indicators is chosen. The first indicator in order to evaluate the profitability of a specific project is

the net present value (NPV) that is the sum of all the present values of the cash-flows corresponding to the project.

$$NPV = \sum_{t=1}^{n_y} \frac{FV}{(1+r)^t} = -I_0 + \sum_{t=1}^{n_y} \frac{AnnualRevenue - OperationCost}{(1+r)^t} \quad (2)$$

where I_0 represents the initial cost of the project assumed to be paid at time $t = 0$. *AnnualRevenue* and *OperationCost* refers to the annual income obtained by selling the energy generated at year t (q_t) (kW) at a price p_t (Euro/kW), and to the annual operation and maintenance costs respectively and r refers to the discount rate.

The second indicator is the internal rate of return (IRR) that is the rate of return that makes the net present value of all cash flows from a particular investment equal to zero. It is expressed with the next formula:

$$NPV = \frac{FV}{(1+IRR)^t} = 0 \quad (3)$$

The last financial indicator to take into account is the payback period (PBP), which provides the minimum number of years needed to recover the initial investment on a project.

$$\sum_{t=0}^{PBP} NPV \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

3. Statistical analysis of financial indicators

The aim of this section is to analyze the uncertainty of the selected financial indicators for the wave energy farm project considered. Following the methodology proposed in this work, we define the socioeconomic scenario based on the following assumptions:

1. Energy price is set to 0.1 Euros/kWh.
2. A nominal interest rate of 8% is fixed with a 3% expected inflation resulting in a 5% real interest rate. This is assumed to be Real Rate of Interest a company is willing to accept and will be used as the discount rate.

3. Initial project's cost are incurred and paid at year 0, that meaning that no external financing is needed for the construction period.
4. OPEX is supposed to account for 5 % of the initial cost of the project. This is an average value obtained from literature.
5. A first estimate of 0.55 Euros/kWh is set for the feed in tariff in order to obtain profits from the investments. Lower values were tested, however, these tariffs produced unrealistic results due to the large proportion of negative IRR and PBP. A detailed sensitivity analysis of the results to different feed in tariffs is presented in the next section.

Figure 8: Mean cash-flow for the 10000 generated life-cycle.

With these assumptions, the cash flow analysis is performed for each of the 10.000 simulated life-cycle, obtaining then a series of 10.000 IRR,NPV

and PBP values. In figure 8 the mean cash flow is shown with a bar diagram. The green dark bars represent the free cash flow accumulative path while the green clear bars represent the income (sales and feed in tariff); the blue bars represents the revenue (Income minus the OPEX) and the blue solid and red dotted lines represent the maximum and minimum free cash flow. The time evolution of the mean cash flow suggest that the mean net present value of the investment is positive. However, the blue and red lines represent the maximum and minimum NPV showing that a negative NPV is also possible. A complete replacement of the devices is foreseen at the thirteenth year resulting in a change in the sign of the cash-flow series is observed. The maximum free cash flow line becomes positive before the replacement reflecting net positive contribution to NPV. Note that the separation between the minimum and maximum values is the highest. This implies that at the end of the cash flow the maximum NPV is positive and the minimum NPV is negative. The difference between maximum and minimum is 2.5 Million Euros. This indicates a great uncertainty induced by the interannual variability of the wave climate. This variability is expressed in terms of the coefficient of variation (standard deviation divided by the mean) in table 2.

Consequently, it can be concluded that the variability derived from randomness in energy fluxes produces the uncertainty in the economic performance of the farms and this can be measured through the statistical distribution of the economic indicators selected. In figure 9 the mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation of wave energy flux are represented. From this figure, it can be concluded that coefficient of variation of wave energy resource should be an important value for wave energy projects location assessment due to its high importance in financial returns. Therefore, as a recommendation for the promotion of wave energy project, locations with a low coefficient of variation and low standard deviation are suggested, for instance near the low latitudes in the Southern hemisphere (for instance on the Chilean coast where the average wave power is high and the coefficient of variation is low).

In figure 10 different life-cycles are compared. For case 1, a life cycle with a high production is simulated, and hence a positive NPV is obtained. It is observed that the positive balance is reached after 22 years of operation. In the second case where a less productive life-cycle is chosen, we observe that the accumulated NPV does not reach a positive value. Therefore, it can

Element	Coefficient of Variation
Wave flux	1.39
Power production	0.128
IRR	0.08
PBP	0.12

Table 2: Coefficient of variation of wave flux, wave production IRR and PBP

concluded that the variability of financial indicators has been analyzed as a result of the influence of the wave climate. Then, it is also concluded that in order to study the performance of a wave energy farm a long data series is needed in order to capture all the met-ocean variability.

The present methodology provides a statistical approach analysis of IRR, NPV and PBP by simulating life-cycle production. In figures 11 to 13 the Cumulative density function (CDF) of the financial indicators IRR, NPV and PBP are shown. In Figure 11 the CDF of IRR and the adjustment to a log-normal distribution are represented (the best fit for these data). It is important to point out that based, on the previous assumptions, the mean IRR is nearly 5.6 %, that is a very low value for an investment. This means that although the benefits can reach a maximum value of 8% this investment represents a high financial risk. The high standard deviation of the distribution(0.45).

Figure 12 represents the CDF of the NPV distribution. The best fit for this data is also a log-normal distribution. The Expected value for this indicator is 828.905 Euros, and the standard deviation for this variable is also high, 624.415 Euros. In the interval between $\mu(NPV) \pm \sigma(NPV)$ ($828905 \pm 624415Eur$) we find the 66% of the occurrences.

Lastly, In figure 13, the CDF of the PBP is shown. In order to fit these data ,the PBP that were greater than project lifetime (25 year) were not taken into consideration (only 0.025 % of the cases). Then this graph presents the truncated distribution. These data fit a t-student distribution. The mean PBP is 21.22 years, and the standard deviation is 2.5 years. This fact means that the NPV reach positive values near the end of the lifetime.

Figure 9: Mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation of wave flux

From the analysis of this figure, the anomalous situation that emerges when the initial investment is recovered before the general replacement is treated. This fact influence the first part of the curve, where the fit of the t-student is worse due to these anomalies.

4. Sensitivity analysis: feed in tariff

In this section a sensitivity analysis is performed on the feed in tariffs. As said before, existing feed in tariffs are not sufficient to guarantee positive profits for the WECs. In this section a set of feed in tariffs will be studied in order to obtain the minimum tariff for the device studied in this paper. The learning process is introduced through a learning curve coefficient affecting

Figure 10: Comparison between 2 life-cycles: top panels, the yearly accumulated production and lower panels associated the cash flow

the investment costs in the future.

All the results obtained until up to this point now derive from the analysis of a 4 WECs wave farm. However, the improvement obtained from repetitive construction cycles has to be considered in order to approximate to the actual field conditions.

The approach to the problem will be based on two steps, initially the sensitivity analysis on feed in tariffs will be performed without a learning process. This way the effect of different feed in tariffs on the financial performance of the project will be isolated. Figure 14 shows this analysis. Note how the minimum feed in tariff required to achieve a positive mean IRR is 0.4 Euros/kWh. Also if a 10% IRR is achieved a feed in tariff of 0.8 Euro/kWh

Figure 11: Cumulative distribution function for the IRR with a lognormal distribution

Figure 12: Cumulative distribution function for the NPV with a lognormal distribution

is needed to reach that value. This corroborates the theory explained in [4] regarding the insufficiency of the actual feed in tariffs. Also another notice-

Figure 13: Cumulative distribution function for the PBP with an extreme value distribution

able issue is the difference between the minimum and maximum IRR for each feed in tariff. For example if a feed in tariff of 0.5 is fixed then the difference between the minimum and maximum IRR is 4 %. This also corroborates the idea explained in the previous subsection on the huge influence that marine climate has on financial indicators. It is important to highlight that the IRR does not reach positive occurrences until 0.3 Euros/kWh.

Another noteworthy issue is how the difference between maximum and minimum is higher as the feed in tariffs increase. This is more evidence of the variability of power production. As the feed in tariff increases, it increases also the revenue, making the power production is more significant in the cash flow analysis. Actually feed in tariffs amplify variability in production when transforming kW into euros. Consequently, a high feed in tariff maximizes the importance of power production in cash flow and it increases variability.

In figure 14, the NPV is also analyzed (taking into account the hypothesis outlined in previous section). The point at which the mean net present value starts to be positive correspond approximately to a 0.6 Euros/kWh, that is a very high feed in tariff comparing with the current values. Moreover, for

the same feed in tariff, the difference between the minimum and maximum NPV is relatively high, approximately 5 million Euros for a feed in tariff of 0.5 Euros/kWh.

As mentioned earlier, on a second step the learning curve is taken into account. Learning curve accounts the process of learning in an industrial process and how it affects the cost of the devices ([17]). Then it is logical that as the number of produced units gets higher, the cost per unit will decrease based on the learning produced per unit. The experience shows that learning process in human activities produce an increase in productivity hence decreasing unit costs. There are very few studies that take into account learning curve in wave energy conversion. In this paper the curve suggested by [4] is used. This curve is specified in the following equation:

$$P = N^{\ln(lc)/\ln(2)} \quad (5)$$

being N the number of WECs produced and lc is the learning curve factor that measures improvements gained when production is doubled (in this case). In this study 3 scenarios are considered. For the optimistic scenario a lc of 0.91 is considered, for the middle 0.86 and for the pessimistic a 0.82. For instance, the middle scenario, with a factor of 0.86 means that when the number of units is doubled the reduction in cost is 14 %. As established previously, this learning curve focus on the technical uncertainty of actual conditions, and allows modeling its impact on financial results. With time and repetition higher levels of efficiency are reached and lower unit costs are obtained. However, the actual learning process rate is a source of advantage or risk for the firms.

In figure 15 the impact of learning curve in the cash-flow analysis is represented. The figure represents the three scenarios specified in the previous paragraph. The 3D plot represents the internal rate of return for the different feed in tariffs and the accumulated number of manufactured units . As the figure shows for all the scenarios for the lowest feed in tariffs and the lowest number of units the internal rate of return is not calculated because it is negative. In the middle scenario it can be seen that for the currents tariffs of 0,22 Euros/kWh (Ireland) a high number of units (nearly 20) need to be considered in order to get an IRR of 10 % or similar. If the percentage of learning is analyzed, this represents a 48% of learning with respect the first

unit, then the cost is expected to diminish 82 % with respect to the first unit. Due to the lack of information, this study was done with a theoretical expression and in reality a drop of the cost in a 48 % is unknown and uncertain. For higher tariffs such 0,4 Euros/kWh a lower number of units is needed in order to get the same IRR.

Figure 16 shows some iso-internal rates of return curves corresponding to the middle scenario. These curves are horizontal sections of the central figure 15 surface. As the feed in tariff grows the internal rate of return has an asymptote, which is obvious as device performance becomes less dependant on the learning process. It is remarkable that the for the base feed in tariff of 0,22 Euros/kWh, 20 units (a 48% drop in the cost) are needed for 10 % IRR , 32 units (a 52% drop in the cost) for the 12 % IRR and 80 units (a 62% drop in the cost) for the 15 % IRR. This fact, gives an idea about the technological risk of this type of inversions and how the feed in tariffs that currently exist are not sufficient for the development of this technology.

This section summarizes the issues and the numbers regarding the subsidies that administrations apply to renewable in order to promote its development. However, the last goal for this study is to provide an abacus for the administrations in order to choose the right feed in tariff (specified for the wave farm of this study) for each case. For this task a set of pdfs is shown in figure 17 for each feed in tariff. These figures can help governments to determine the appropriate feed in tariff to assure a given IRR with a given confidence level. For instance, in the first subfigure with a tariff of 0.25 Euros/kWh an 8% IRR is possible but the probability is very low (0.1 %). This figure give the administration an abacus in order to choose with statistical parameters the right tariff. In this figure it should be highlighted that the shape of the pdf changes as the feed in tariff increases. The pdf moves towards higher IRR and also the pdf has a flatter shape. Figure 17 show how the pdfs mean and standard deviation increase as the feed in tariff increases. The reason is because as the feed in tariff increases the importance of revenues by the energy production increases in the cash flow algorithm and then the variability of production has a major influence on the distribution of IRR. For instance, if nowadays a 10 % is needed with a high level of confidence (95%) a feed in tariff of 0.5 Eur/kWh is needed.

Figure 14: Internal rate of return and Net present value vs different feed in tariffs

5. Conclusions

The aim of this paper is to examine the uncertainty of the economic analysis on wave energy farms. A cash flow algorithm is developed in order to analyze these uncertainties. A methodology to find out how the wave climate affects the financial performance of a wave energy project is presented first based on a sea state selection technique, a non-linear interpolation technique and a random bootstrapping. The results show that the variability of financial indicators is huge due to the variability of wave climate. The CDFs of IRR, NPV and PBP are fitted to a log-normal distribution, characterized by low mean and high variances. The need for long term climate data series is shown, and its importance is highlighted in order to explain the influence of climate variability in wave farms economic analysis.

The political-legal source of uncertainty is covered next focusing on the feed in tariff influence. The current feed in tariffs is shown to be insufficient. Besides the maximization of the influence of power production variability as the feed in tariff increases is demonstrated. It has been concluded that

Figure 15: Internal rate of return vs number of units and feed in tariff for the different scenarios proposed (the gross lines represent the isolines of IRR)

Figure 16: Curves of iso-internal rate of return for number of units produced vs feed in tariff applied

the feed in tariff is not a very efficient funding mechanism for early stage wave energy technologies. As with respect the effect of considering the learn-

Figure 17: PDF of IRR for the different feed in tariffs

ing curve the analysis evidences that, in order to achieve economic feasibility of a wave energy project, the learning process needs to be taken into account.

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References

- [1] de Andrés, A., Guanche, R., Armesto, J., del Jesus, F., Vidal, C., Losada, I. Time domain model for a two-body heave converter: Model and applications. *Ocean Engineering* 2013;72(0):116 – 123. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2013.06.019>.
- [2] Ayyub, B. *Elicitation of Expert Opinions for Uncertainty and Risks*. Taylor & Francis; 2010. ISBN 9780849310874.
- [3] Beels, C., Troch, P., Kofoed, J.P., Frigaard, P., Kringelum, J.V., Kromann, P.C., et al. A methodology for production and cost assessment of

- a farm of wave energy converters. *Renewable Energy* 2011;36(12):3402 – 3416. doi:10.1016/j.renene.2011.05.019.
- [4] Dalton, G., Alcorn, R., Lewis, T.. A 10 year installation program for wave energy in ireland: A case study sensitivity analysis on financial returns. *Renewable Energy* 2012;40(1):80 – 89. doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2011.09.025.
- [5] O’Connor, M., Lewis, T., Dalton, G.. Techno-economic performance of the pelamis {P1} and wavestar at different ratings and various locations in europe. *Renewable Energy* 2013;50(0):889 – 900. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2012.08.009>.
- [6] O’Connor, M., Lewis, T., Dalton, G.. Operational expenditure costs for wave energy projects and impacts on financial returns. *Renewable Energy* 2013;50(0):1119 – 1131. doi:10.1016/j.renene.2012.08.059.
- [7] Babarit, A., Hals, J., Muliawan, M., Kurniawan, A., Moan, T., Krokstad, J.. Numerical benchmarking study of a selection of wave energy converters. *Renewable Energy* 2012;41(0):44 – 63. doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2011.10.002.
- [8] IHCantabria, . ENOLA Project. 2011.
- [9] Hernandez-Brito, J., Monagas, V., Gonzalez, J., Schallenberg, J., Llins, O.. Vision for marine renewables in the canary islands. In: 4th International Conference on Ocean Energy, 17 October, Dublin. 2012,.
- [10] Reguero, B., Menndez, M., Mndez, F., Mnguez, R., Losada, I.. A global ocean wave (gow) calibrated reanalysis from 1948 onwards. *Coastal Engineering* 2012;65(0):38 – 55. doi: 10.1016/j.coastaleng.2012.03.003.
- [11] Camus, P., Mendez, F.J., Medina, R.. A hybrid efficient method to downscale wave climate to coastal areas. *Coastal Engineering* 2011;58(9):851 – 862. doi:10.1016/j.coastaleng.2011.05.007.
- [12] DNV, . SESAM Users Manual, WADAM; 2008.
- [13] de Andrés, A., Guanche, R., Meneses, L., Vidal, C., Losada, I.J.. Factors that influence array layout on wave energy farms. *Ocean Engineering*(submitted) 2013;.

- [14] Espejo, A., Minguez, R., Tomas, A., Menendez, M., Mendez, F., Losada, I. Directional calibrated wind and wave reanalysis databases using instrumental data for optimal design of off-shore wind farms. In: OCEANS, 2011 IEEE - Spain. 2011, p. 1 –9. doi:10.1109/Oceans-Spain.2011.6003592.
- [15] Harris R.E., J.L.W.J.. Mooring systems for wave energy converters: A review of design issues and choices. 3rd International Conference on Marine Renewable Energy, Blyth, UK 2004;.
- [16] Donald G Newnan, P., Lavelle, J.. Essentials of Engineering Economic Analysis. Engineering Press; 1998. ISBN 9781576450284.
- [17] Wright, T.P.. Factors Affecting the Cost of Airplanes. Journal of Aeronautical Sciences 1936;3:122–128.